

The Impact of Advertising on Children How Does Advertising Influence Children?

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Abstract:

Advertisements do have a large impact on the audiences. Every day children are exposed to the selling messages of advertisers via mass media. It clarifies that advertisements really are one of the most powerful and strongest medium of mass communication.

Though advertisements help us to become aware of the products in the market, they have their negative effects also. Children today are exposed to all types of advertisements on the various media like the television, print media and internet as well. In fact, everyone is bombarded by advertisements everywhere nowadays. It can be said that advertising is a pervasive influence on children and adolescents, although Children in general are more susceptible and get easily influenced by advertisements.

Children are defenseless and innocent. When a marketer advertises a product on television, they do not understand that it is a business and their main aim is to sell. They do not understand that advertisers try to push their products and market in such a way that children want to buy it. Children take everything at face value and believe without a doubt the messages in the advertisements. Advertisements are made in such a way as to attract the attention of children. Children do not understand it to be marketing strategy. Children are an extremely vulnerable target audience and get easily carried away. Hence, in this study we are going to understand how advertising influence children?

Keywords: Advertising, Children Phycology, Mass Media, Mass Communication

1. INTRODUCTION

Advertising is hardly a recent human endeavor; Archaeologists have uncovered signs of advertising property for rent dating back to ancient Rome and Pompeii. Town criers were another early form of advertising. As an industry, advertising did not take off until the arrival of the various mass media: printing, radio, and television. Nevertheless, the concerns over advertising targeting children preceded both radio and television. The British Parliament passed a law in 1874 intended to protect children from the efforts of merchants to induce them to buy products and take on debt [3].

Commercial appeals to children, however, did not become a commonplace until the advent and widespread adoption of television and grew exponentially with the advent of cable television, which allowed programmers to develop the entire channels of child-oriented programming and advertising [3] The advertising industry spends \$ 12 billion per year on ads targeted to children, bombarding young audiences with persuasive messages through media such as television and the Internet.

Compounding the growth in channels for advertising targeting children has been another development: the privatization of children's media use. A recent study found that the majority of all U.S. Children have televisions in their bedrooms. Many children also have uncontrolled access to computers, meaning that much of media (and advertising) content that children view is in

context of missing parents monitoring and supervision [3].

These two trends-the growth in advertising channels reaching children and the privatization of children's media use-led to a dramatic increase in the advertising directly targeted for children's eyes and austeres. It is estimated that advertisers spend more than \$ 12 billion a year to reach the youth market and that children will view more than 40,000 commercials each year. These figures represent dramatic increases over those of the 1970s. [3] So it is no wonder that advertisers are racing to attract children to their corner and keep them buying their brands. [8]

The ad film makers are formulating fresh ways of enticing consumers to buy products. If an advertisement for a product attracts the consumer, they tend to buy it frequently, or at least buy it once. If a company has to survive in this competitive world, they have to project the image of their products in such a way that they pick up the maximum sales, when they hit stores.

The best way to persuade the consumer to stick to the product of the particular brand, when there is a lot of choices available to them on the market - through attractive ads. However, ad film makers should remember that the commercials can also have a negative impact on people, especially young children. In this article, I have

presented some of the most visible effects of advertising on children, positive as well as negative.

2. The Economic Market of Children

2.1. Companies and Children

Companies are very interested in children as consumers. Kids “are seen as multi-taskers, risk takers, explorers, early adopters of new technology and looking to make a personal statement.” Companies are aware that marketing directed at those age groups is key. This is why they conduct a lot of research to determine what children like:

Marketers employ child psychologists, cultural anthropologists, review academic literature on child development, send experts into homes, stores and fast food restaurants, organize focus groups, study children's drawings, dreams and fantasy lives, and apply the findings to ads and product designs. [6]

Because children are more easily impressionable, it is more difficult for companies to maintain and establish a long term relationship. McNeal claims that children will be familiar with approximately 200 product brands before starting first grade: “Ronald McDonald’s face is recognized by nearly 96% of American children. Even young children are familiar with McDonald’s logo, the golden arches.” [17]

Companies spend millions of dollars per year in marketing. For example, McDonald’s spent \$723 million in marketing only in 2004 [17]. To reach children on a larger scale, they form alliances, also called cross-promotions, with other companies such as toy companies, film production companies and sports leagues: “An analysis of promotions for a new children’s movie, Shrek the Third, found 17 separate food promotions linked to the movie. The promotions represented 75 different processed food products including McDonald’s Happy Meals, Kellogg’s Froot Loops cereal and Kellogg’s Frosted S’Mores Pop Tarts.” [4] Cross promotions or tie-in promotions are very popular now and may double or even triple the volume of weekly sales of children’s meals [17]. According to a report from the Public Health Agency of Canada, McDonald’s perfected the tie-in promotion strategy. This promotional tactic, used by the fast food chain, has been recognized as one of the five greatest marketing accomplishments of the 20th century [6].

Another example of cross promotion involves the affiliation of the fast food chain KFC to the popular video game Guitar Hero. This video game allows players to (relatively) move while they are having fun (which is rarer with this type of game). The KFC chain was therefore offering, in 2008, meals called “The Loaded Box Meal”, since this meal contained 1210 calories. It included a 32 ounce soft drink served in a collectible

“Guitar Hero” glass, chicken fingers, one piece of dark meat chicken, and a chicken sandwich called the “Snacker”, two side dishes, and a cookie. This rich meal was also served in a cardboard box with Guitar Hero graphics [17].

Therefore, to successfully attract young people, companies choose a combination of various methods including contests and games, toys, the playground, the use of fictitious or popular characters, the use of different attractive colours, etc [10]. Using these other means provides numerous promotion opportunities among children, ensures a frequent exposure to the brand and often associates the product with experiences which contribute to brand awareness and loyalty. Ads in magazines disguised as editorial content; clothes, toys and books featuring logos; contests, advertising tricks and purchase gifts are other practices commonly used by advertisers to reach children [17].

2.2 Brand Recognition

Among the various brands on the many markets, the brands that are most often recognized are fast food chain brands (92.9%). It will not come as a surprise that a study about brand recognition by children claims that they have less difficulty recognizing the brands they are interested in: “Brands for which children are the primary target segment will inevitably be marketed more directly to children. When messages are tailored to captivate children’s attention, information may be more easily processed and stored, thereby increasing children’s subsequent brand recognition.” [17] It seems that infants as young as 6 months old are able to form mental images of logos and mascots. Furthermore, loyalty to a brand may be established by children as young as 2 years old. Children recognize brands through the various characteristics of their packaging or their logo. For example, attractive and vibrant colours, shapes and fictitious characters allow children to recognize the brand and to ask their parents for it [10]. Also, brands are requested according to their popularity. At the early age of three, children begin judging their peers based on their consumption habits and the products they use: The present results show that children as young as 3 willingly judge their peers. They see other children as popular or unpopular, fun or boring, because of the brands they use. Such judgments suggest that, at an early age, children attribute great importance to the use of branded products to cultivate and promote self-image. This fashion phenomenon may also be observed in the food industry and the same study found that children’s eating habits are greatly influenced by this brand phenomenon [17].

3. The Persuasive Aspect of Advertising to Children

Two important information processing tasks are required for any person to achieve a mature understanding of advertising messages. First, the individual must be able to distinguish between commercial and noncommercial content. In other words, an individual must be able to differentiate the ads from the programs.

The persuasive dimension of advertising and marketing is not easily identifiable for a child. The younger he is, the blurrier this dimension is. An American medical institute has shown that a child under the age of 8 generally does not have the required cognitive abilities to denote this persuasive dimension of ads, even when program/commercial separation devices ("GoBots will be back after these messages") are used. As children reach the age of 4–5 years, they typically perceive a categorical distinction between commercials and programming, but primarily on the basis of affective ("commercials are funnier") or perceptual ("commercials are shorter") cues only [3]. As for children under 4, they do not always know the difference between the program and an ad. They may think that the ad is part of the program they are watching.

Do children really recognize the change between their television show and an ad this question is greatly addressed and answers vary. Livingstone proposes that a child aged 3 to 4 reacts to the change between the program and the ad, because of the different audiovisual characteristics of these two types of content rather than the understanding of the difference between those contents. As well, this researcher found that a child aged 2 to 72 months 'obeys' to the "centering" phenomenon, so they react to the ad's prime attributes, such as colour or sound, in order to determine if they like the ad or not [17].

The second essential cognitive task involved in a mature comprehension of advertising is the ability to recognize the persuasive intent of advertising and to apply that knowledge in the child's understanding of the advertising message. In other words, mature persuasive intent comprehension involves not only the recognition that the advertiser has a perspective different from the viewer and that advertisers intend to persuade their audience to want to buy their products, but also that such persuasive communication is biased, and that biased messages must be interpreted differently than unbiased messages [17].

Basic developmental research on egocentrism and perspective taking, along with a great deal of evidence specifically examining developmental differences in the comprehension of persuasive intent within advertisements, establishes clearly that most children younger than 7–8 years of age do not recognize the persuasive intent of commercial appeals. However, there is far less research examining whether and at what ages children begin to appreciate that advertising messages are

inherently biased or on when children begin to develop strategies to counteract the bias within these messages. It is clear that both of these abilities are dependent upon the child's development of the ability to understand the persuasive intent of advertising, meaning that mature comprehension of advertising occurs no earlier than age 7–8 years on average [17].

Livingstone found that by the age of 8, most children are able to differentiate commercial messages and television programs: "Before then, they also find it more difficult than adults to distinguish reality from fiction: for example, when actors or humans are used it is assumed to be real, while fiction is limited to cartoons, puppets or other fictitious characters; the notion of an actor paid to pretend to be someone else can be difficult for them to grasp" [14]. It is after the age of 8 that the child would be more capable of understanding the persuasive dimension of advertising and from 10 to 12 that they could even be critical about it: "beyond the age of eight, children have greater ability to respond to advertising in a more sophisticated way but research has determined that many children as old as 10-12 years of age will not use their critical evaluation skills to interpret ads unless prompted to do so." [19] Kapferer claims that children do not understand the persuasive aspect of advertising, which Option consummators confirms:

Since they are captive, they are a golden audience for advertisers. When it comes to advertising, they are particularly vulnerable because of the unequal power relationship between an advertiser, who has significant financial resources to create an ad, and the child, credulous and naïve [14].

Further investigation is needed to establish the upper age boundary of children who are uniquely vulnerable to televised commercial persuasion as a function of normative developmental limitations on their information-processing capabilities. Nonetheless, a key conclusion of the task force, which is supported by a strong base of empirical evidence, is that young children below 7–8 years of age clearly lack an understanding of the persuasive intent of television advertising [17]. Children therefore risk being wronged during the consumption process [14].

Also, since they do not understand advertising's persuasive dimension, children under 8 have great confidence in it. A study conducted among children of an elementary school shows that less than 50% of them were aware of the persuasive dimension of advertisements [2].

4. Children in Family Purchasing Decisions

More than 50 million children and adolescents represent a large part of the market and they influence the parents buying decisions items [12]. It can be stated that family dynamics have changed over the last few years. Dagnaud

highlights “how much the family model and, within it, the child’s place, have evolved.” [7] The overvaluing of children and the undermining of parental authority are signs of this change. Codes are getting blurry, which is also reflected in the advertising industry. Pester power marketing targets children who, unable to purchase products for themselves, nag, pester and beleaguer their parents into purchasing Harmful or useless products for them [5].

Children have a greater influence and effect the families buying behaviour. For example, there is a 75% desire for a pre-teen or child to have an Apple electronic Garget around the world, mostly in advanced countries. A reliable research observes that 73% of people communicate with at least one family member a day by phone, email, or even personally. The research further states that 65% of 'Adult children' reside within 1-2 hours of driving from their parents and even as they are grown, they still continue to play a major role in the family behavior of the consumer [23].

According to "Union nationale des associations familiales" advertising is affected by the tangent that is the increase of the child’s influencing power:

Parents therefore appear to be influenced twice: directly, through the advertising discourse, and indirectly through their offspring’s role. A consensus is far from reached regarding advertising’s influence on children’s influencing behaviour, though most researchers come to the conclusion that there is an actual influence in cases where the ads are about products created for children. However, this influence does not seem to have this automatic characteristic it is often criticized for. This influence is sometimes difficult to assess: a jingle or a slogan a child sings or repeats all day long may help add the brand to their parents’ evoked set, even if the parents have not even been exposed to the ad itself. These are of course linked advertising and infantile influences but they are quite tricky to apprehend [26].

During the eighties, ads were directed at adults. At the turn of the nineties, the target gradually became children. Noticing the shift in influencing power within the family model, advertisers had to adapt to try and influence the behaviours of the new target audience: “Cognitive, affective and also moral elements forged the structure of the rationale. They discuss the child and its place within society. It is noted that the two main characteristics that gravitate around this image of the child are parental absence and group mind.” [7] Also, as previously mentioned, it seems that children greatly influence family purchases – around \$15 billion annually [25].

Marketers are often interested in families because they serve children as great influencers and consumers [23]. In

other words, children may not have as much economic power as adults, but they certainly have a voice when it comes to family purchases [9]. Influencers here provide information to other members of the family about a product or service. The market that Involves children is large and important because they have a major influence on family decision-making on budget allocation and purchase choices. For example, the urban Chinese children are known for influencing two thirds of their parents purchasing decision directly or indirectly [23]. Also, According to the IED, child recommendations (up to 10 years old) reach about 68% for dairy products, 65% for candy, 40% for the type of vacation and even 19% and 11% for the clothing chosen by the mother and father.” [9] Generally speaking, 67% of children make requests when they visit the grocery store with their parents. They influence 43% of family purchases and the overall amount of purchases influenced by children is 15% [21]. Because of the wide range of commercial messages meticulously targeted to specific segments of the child audience, children seem to have become less dependent on their parents in learning about consumer values. It is possible that entertainment and advertising aimed at young children shortens the period during which parents are the primary socializing force in the lives of their children. Although today’s children ad adolescents have the spending power to utilize their consumer skills, they still often lack the maturity to think carefully about buying decisions. Media literacy research is needed to understand how children and adolescents can be taught to make thoughtful consumer decisions, as well as how to protect them from commercial pressures to buy quickly and impulsively [15].

Joël Brée, professor, confirms that children are able to influence their parents regarding consumption. He speaks of the immediacy phenomenon, the fact that the child wishes to acquire the product immediately when he spots it:

By definition, the child’s life is ruled by a logic of immediacy. For him, desire requires rapid satisfaction. Brands have understood this well: special transactions and other “product gifts” (remember the Bonus!) encourage impulse purchases. In this context, the relation to brand and to the world it conveys via advertising plays an important role. However, the process is different for “public” objects of consumption: beyond the child’s impulse (individual decision), the desire must first be validated by the group he is a part of... or would like to be a part of! In this context, the sharing process is part of this decision. Think of those stickers, whose collection depends on the ability to trade, a factor of integration within the group and of identity development [17].

Certain statistics help explain children's influential role. According to the study conducted by Minot, three parameters, other than basic parameters such as age, should be considered when addressing the child's influencing power: the nature of the products, the buying act and the behavioral roles in relation, as well as the notion of influence [21].

5. Television, Children and Advertising

5.1. Television

Estimates of the number of commercials viewed by young children range from 19,000 And 22,000 commercials per year or about three hours of television advertising every week of the year [13].

Televised advertising has long been chosen for its ability to convey emotion using both image and sound. And, these last few years, we have seen the development of several new techniques and media for Advertising:

Televised advertising is a good medium to raise awareness about a new product, because it reaches People very quickly and it conveys ambiance and emotion quite successfully. Yet, it does have its limit. More and more, we are seeing that the television advertising itself is not enough to motivate The consumer; The cause may be found in its evanescent nature and in its rather limited length: 20 to 30 seconds To ensure an effective strategy, marketing should be a way of approaching the consumer not only through Television, but with other media as well [11].

However, the television medium remains the most used to broadcast advertising. Of all the Advertisements from agri-food companies, 75% are for television [2]. The agri-food market mainly uses television to reach children, and with good reason:

Television is widely predominant in children's responses regarding advertising sources. It is linked to over two thirds of desires and 63.2% of requests generated by advertising in the major media. Television's impact through advertising is the development of a child's desires Confirmed [9]. According to a report released in 2008 by Option Consummators, 90% of children say that television is The focus of their interests [24]: "[...] In the US, 17% of babies under one Year old and 48% of babies aged one to two are exposed to the device at least one hour per day. And actually, pre-school children (six and under) spend as much time in front of the screens as they play Outside "[26].

5.2. The Importance of Television for Children

In terms of daily activities, television is in third place for children, after sleeping and going to school [21]. At the commemoration ceremony of the 20th anniversary of the *Convention internationale des Droits de l'enfant*, Jacques

Brodeur presented a study that showed the importance of television in children's lives: "To get an idea of the power of media's influence among young people, Foundation Kaiser evaluated the place of the media in their lives: 58% eat in front of the screen, 42% have the TV on from morning to night, 53% have a TV in their bedroom, 49% don't have rules to follow regarding content and the amount of time they spend watching it, 81% cannot count on any parental supervision." [17].

In Canada, Children aged 2 to 11 watch an average of 14.6 hours of television per week [17]. This number is higher in Quebec (francophones), i.e. 15.1 hours of weekly consumption. "Close to 20% of the time these children spend in front of the TV is spent watching commercials; it appears that on average a young viewer would see 30,000 per year." Since children represent a global market of \$600 billion per year, it is no surprise that they are so targeted by commercials [17].

According to a study conducted in October 2007 for the Ministry of Health, 47% say that the advertising seen on television encourages them to eat and drink, 62% of them request what they saw to their parents... and 91% say they get what they want because of their parents' weakness." [17].

5.3. The Types of Products Advertised

Regarding food advertising, non-diet products are highly advertised to children, whereas products related to diet are more often advertised to adults [26]. The non-diet products advertised are those of fast food chains, soft drinks, snacks, candy, and cereals that are high in sugar: "A study that was conducted in parallel in France and Quebec at the beginning of the nineties (Watiez & Dubois, 1997) shows that televised ads about food broadcast during young people's prime time mostly concern sugar-sweetened products and beverages. The broadcasting of these advertisements follows young viewers' television watching curve." [26].

A study mentioned by the Union des consommateurs report shows that most food ads featured on television promote products of low nutritional quality:

Out of a total of 135 food products these ads were portraying, 73% (i.e. 99 products out of 135) are not part of Canada's Food Guide to Healthy Eating. It displays all types of snacks, candy, prepared foods and various beverages. Researchers did a similar exercise in English Canada by focusing on the commercials broadcast on Saturday mornings, from 7 to 11am on five television stations. Out of 160 hours of programming, 147 commercials were reviewed, among which half (74 out of 147) advertised food. Among the ads created to promote foods, about fifty represented foods of low nutritional quality, fast food restaurants or sugar-sweetened cereal [26].

It seems the time spent watching television has a very significant influence on children as young as three years old, by driving them to ask their parents to get them to buy those marketed products: For example, a cohort study of over 10,000 9 to 14 year olds in the USA found that those who spent more time with television/videos/games showed larger BMI increases a year later. These effects were stronger for those who are already overweight, suggesting a cumulative effect over time [17]. The British Birth Cohort Study, similarly, followed up over 11,000 children from the ages of five to thirty, revealing that the amount of weekend television viewing in early childhood continues to influence BMI in adulthood [15].

5.4. Children Advertisement and its Effects

Television advertising is the number one source of information about new products; and most children would not consider purchasing a product that was not highly advertised on television [8]. Via the magic of television deals to broadcast program which can have profound effects on the developing world and the children to change their lives. No doubt with the development of new networks and satellite television in the world scene, the children will be more vulnerable to the effects of various television In other words, the potential impact of the television spectrum can be put on their young viewers, with the widespread application of this media has become more widespread [1]. Marketers estimated that kids under the age of 12 years old directly spent over \$200 billion each year [18].

After the family television programs and personalities of the most important factors in forming a child's education is one Television teacher is a powerful, yet dangerous. Imitation, along with the concept, personality development and behavioral problems, the effects of television on children is a special way into his mind. When watching TV programs are on track and learning programs offered via television, the unconscious is far, Children are not aware that their behavior and the behavior of others are acquired, the effectiveness of television can be considered as one of the most important aspect of watching TV programs about the impact of TV ads has been a lot of viewers, especially children television as the most influential instrument of mass communication, is considered most suitable by the Propaganda In view of the world's population, mostly young people communicate with the outside world through television, the most important means of mass communication that we seek [1].

One strong argument as to why TV advertisements were geared towards children has been the fact that children have a lot of money to spend. Since the advertisement is to position products to the target consumers; therefore, advertisements to kids are appropriate. Children as

observed represent a huge, profitable, and developing or growing market to advertisers [16]. Advertising to children below the age of 16 is governed by some clear rules. Advertisements featuring children must contain nothing that is likely to result in their physical, mental or moral harm. Children are bound to develop considerable abilities to counter-argue against commercial messages. Television advertising has a powerful influence on children's product preferences and choices and at least a moderate role in perception and usage of products such as cigarettes, alcohol and heavily sugared or non-nutritious foods [23]. Since television has such a massive presence, public concern has understandably focused on the possible negative impact of television advertising on children [8].

The researchers performed many studies have concluded that watching television advertising, on attitudes, life style and consumption pattern of the behavior of the audience, including children, affected [1]. A variety of studies using differing methodologies find that children recall content from the ads to which they've been exposed. Product preference has been shown to occur with as little as a single commercial exposure and to strengthen with repeated exposures. Most importantly, studies have shown that product preferences affect children's product purchase requests and that these requests do influence parents' purchasing decisions [3]. However, the effect of the various factors such as age, Social class, economic, message presentation, family structure and relationships governing the time watching television. For example, children who are at an early age because of limited cognitive abilities, the reality of what they think of television viewing and much closer to reality television programs that children know of content that are most affected. Accordingly, the effectiveness of children's age and years of TV ads, most children that age are high [1].

There are also strong family relationships and causes children to be influenced by television programs. Parents with children studying the reality of online life that it can monitor and control, they are more aware of advertising and commercial purposes and the negative view about these programs is more critical than. While the relationships between family members that it is hostile, Children may achieve the advertised product, make life difficult for their parents. Affect the presentation of advertising messages are considered an important factor [1].

Duration of exposure to advertisements, other factors affect them [1]. According to Keeney, Cannizzo and Flavell (1967) "children who watch four or more hours of television (TV) a day are more likely to believe claims made by advertisers" [23].

The more fundamental concern regarding the effects of advertising on children relates to questions of potential harm resulting from exposure [3]. A variety of research findings are relevant to this issue. Several studies, for example, have found that parent-child conflicts occur commonly when parents deny their children's product purchase requests that were precipitated by advertising. Considerable research has examined advertising's cumulative effect on children's eating habits. Studies have documented that a high percentage of advertisements targeting children feature candy, fast foods, and snacks and that exposure to such advertising increases consumption of these products. While consumption of non-nutritious foods per se may not be harmful, overconsumption of these products, particularly to the exclusion of healthier food, is linked to obesity and poorer health. Several studies have found strong associations between increases in advertising for nonnutritious foods and rates of childhood obesity [3].

A variety of studies have found a substantial relationship between children's viewing of tobacco and alcohol ads and positive attitudes toward consumption of such products. Children find many such commercials attractive (e.g., Joe Camel, the Budweiser frogs) and consequently have high brand awareness of such products and positive attitudes toward them. These products and their spokes-characters have been found to be featured in programming and publications frequently viewed by minors, and reviews of this research (including the Surgeon General's analysis) conclude that advertising of them contributes to youth smoking and drinking [3].

Critics have also expressed concern regarding the prevalence of advertising of violent media, such as movies and video games, targeting children. Three reports by the Federal Trade Commission found considerable support for such charges, and while studies have not directly assessed the impact of such advertising, it is highly likely that such ads do affect children's media preferences [3].

According to the Committee on Communications (2006), various inquiries and findings have shown that young children known to be younger than 8 years are cognitively and psychologically unprotected or powerless against advertising. In the late 1970s, the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) held some trials, studied the existing research and came to the conclusion that it is a discriminating and deceptive act to advertise to children less than 6 years. While carrying out this research accordingly, there was a realisation that a foetus although undeveloped and unborn, responds to sounds that emanate from the television [23].

5.5. Positive Effects of Advertisements on Children

1. Commercials make children aware of new products existing in the market which increases and broadens their knowledge about the newest innovations, in technological terms and other aspects.
2. Productive advertisement which center on healthy and useful products, may improve the health and quality of child life, if made attractive and appealing.

5.6. Negative Effects of Advertisement on Children

Children show increasing signs when there is an issue in controlling their weight of being the worst generation yet. Nixon (2004) goes on to illustrate how advertisement could be harmful to children through the under listed points [22]:

1. Advertisements encourage the children to persuade their parents to purchase the products shown in the commercials, whether useful or not. The little ones tend to get adamant, if the product is not bought for them.
2. Children often tend to misinterpret the messages conveyed in commercials. They overlook the positive side and concentrate more on the negatives.
3. Many advertisements in the present times include dangerous stunts, which can be performed only by experts. Even though the commercials broadcast the statutory warnings with the ad, kids often try to imitate the stunts at home, with fatal results.
4. Flashy advertisements broadcast in television generate impulse shopping in children.
5. Children, after watching the glitter of commercials, often lose the ability to live a life without materialistic joy.
6. Kids usually get more attracted towards costly branded products, such as jeans and accessories. They disregard the inexpensive, but useful ones that are not shown in the commercials.
7. Advertisements have an indirect effect on the behavior of children. They might develop temper tantrums, when deprived of the latest toys and clothes that are shown in commercials.
8. The personal preferences in clothing, toys, food and luxurious of children are altered by advertisements, to a great extent.
9. Junk foods, such as pizzas, burgers and soft drinks, are heavily promoted during children's TV viewing time. This develops a craving for fatty, sugary and fast foods in kids, thereby affecting their health adversely.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Advertisements do have a large impact on the children because children are more vulnerable to advertising. Different laws in different countries to limit the number of ads used to be, kind, Content and timing of the broadcast ad covers For example, advertisements for toys for children to play in Greece is limited to late night hours Australia and Belgium, and in advertisements broadcast during children's broadcasts A few minutes before it is banned. Some researchers believe that it is better to limit excessive advertising Products to raise awareness of parents of children and to discuss with them about products and promotions the researchers say understanding the power to limit excessive growth of advertising and the guys decide to delay.

Children should not be banned entirely from watching television only because of the harm it may cause to them but they should be encouraged to watch channels that are strictly for them and educative. These channels are well monitored because the agents are aware of their target audience. The use of cables are also encouraged because of the advantage of pass codes that bar children from watching channels that are likely to damage their psychological thinking. So parents and teachers should increase the will power and self-esteem in children, so bring the kids once I see ads that are part of the economy, society correctly imagined to be the means of advertising. Techniques and methods of advertising to children should be taught and developed the power to judge and criticize them. The ad cannot promote, or sell their goods to attract customers. It can only draw attention to the customer, to persuade him to buy. If the buyer has enough information to evaluate the ads and advertisers.

In general we can say the main criticisms against television advertising on children include:

1. Unlimited and uncontrolled effects of advertising on children
2. Promote consumerism and false needs
3. Disorders of children on the farm and Health
4. Create gender discrimination.

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made.

1. Parents should monitor what their children view on TV.
2. Parents should limit their spending unnecessary spending on their children demands.
3. Government should regulate misleading advertisements.
4. Children should be educated by their parents on the differences between TV shows and commercials.

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